

UV and fluorescence spectral characteristics of Ciprofloxacin-Betacyclodextrin inclusion complex

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Enhanced UV absorption ($a = 4.4$ fold) and fluorescence emission ($k = 4.6$ fold) was observed in the case of Ciprofloxacin on complexation with Betacyclodextrin (1 : 1 M). This could enhance the precession in the analysis of Ciprofloxacin in formulations or biological samples for bio-availability studies.

Ciprofloxacin ($C_{17}H_{19}FN_3O_3$, labeled as CIP) is chemically 1-cyclo-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolone carboxylic acid available as chloride. It is a fluoroquinolone antibacterial reported to have poor stability at accelerated stability conditions¹. Betacyclodextrin, a cyclic Oligosaccharide containing 7 glucose units linked by α -1,4 glycosidic bonds ($C_6H_{10}O_5$, labeled as BCD) is more commonly used in the formation of inclusion complex of various drugs compared to other cyclodextrins due to their molecular geometry and hydrophobic cavity which facilitate the inclusion of hydrophobic drugs of suitable dimension into its cavity². The inclusion complex of CIP with BCD resulted in the enhanced UV absorption and fluorescence emission spectral property. The molecules containing functional groups : $-NH_2$, $-OH$, $-F$ increases the fluorescence emission, while NO_2 , $COOH$ reduces³. The presence of polycyclic aromatic ring coupled with of the functional groups like F^- , NH in Ciprofloxacin could contribute for its fluorescence. Thus the fluorimetric analysis can be utilized with advantage over other methods like UV and HPLC in the trace quantity estimation of either drug or by forming BCD complex, which is quick, simple, cost effective and accurate.

Results and discussion

UV absorption spectral data : The λ_{max} for Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in acidic, neutral and alkaline pH were 278, 276 and 272 nm respectively. However the absorption in alkaline pH (9.2) was more than that at acidic pH (4.2). On complexation with BCD, it was observed that there is no shift in the λ_{max} but, there is an increase in the

molar extinction by 4.4 fold in case of 1 : 1 complex, however, BCD alone do not have UV absorption at 272 nm. The system obeys Beer's law in the range 0.00 to 10.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ at the λ_{max} 272 nm. The absorbance and hence the molar extinction values of the complexes were relatively high compared to the corresponding physical mixtures (Table 1). The value of z increased on increasing the BCD content in the complex and found to be maximum in case of 1 : 1 M complex (337.6) which is a true complex as evidenced by molecular, modeling⁴ and spectral studies.

Fluorescence emission spectral data : The excitation and fluorescence emission wavelength for Ciprofloxacin was found to be 278 and 448 nm, respectively in 0.01 M HCl, whereas, in alkaline and neutral pH the fluorescence intensity was relatively less and hence all observations were made in acidic pH. The emission intensity of the complexes was considerably high compared to the corresponding physical mixture. A plot of fluorescence intensity versus concentration of Ciprofloxacin/preparations was linear in the range 0.00 to 0.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The fluorescence emission intensity of the physical mixtures decreases as the drug content in it was decreased and corresponds to the drug content in it. This indicated that the presence of BCD does not affect the fluorescence of Ciprofloxacin. But the fluorescence intensity of the complexes was higher than those of the physical mixtures. An empirical fluorescence coefficient (k) calculated showed a significant increase in the case of complex compared to the physical mixture. The value of z confirms this observation and attributes to the increased sensitivity of fluorimetric analysis of the Ciprofloxacin by complexation (Table 1). This was attrib-

Table 1. Comparative UV and fluorescence data of Ciprofloxacin-Betacyclodextrin complexes and the corresponding physical mixtures

Ratio of CIP to BCD (w/w)	Molar extinction $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ $a \times 10^3$	%Variation of a with respect to the physical mixture (z)	Fluorescence intensity for 0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution F	Fluorescence coefficient $k \times 10^6 \text{mol}^{-1}$	%Variation of k with respect to the physical mixture (z)
1 : 0	32.03	—	48.6	359.7	—
1 : 0.5	89.57 ^a 130.89 ^b	— 46.10	27.85 ^a 46.1 ^b	836.61 ^a 1384.84 ^b	— 65.5
1 : 1	66.57 ^a 134.5 ^b	— 102.00	20.90 ^a 45.85 ^b	627.84 ^a 1377.33 ^b	— 119.4
1 : 2	42.52 ^a 131.50 ^b	— 209.2	14.0 ^a 43.35 ^b	419.06 ^a 1302.23 ^b	— 210.8
1 : 1 M	29.15 ^a 127.59 ^b	— 337.6	9.65 ^a 45.15 ^b	289.89 ^a 1356.31 ^b	— 367.9

^aValues for the physical mixture.^bValues for the complex.

uted to the fact that BCD offer protective micro environment, leading to enhanced fluorescence of the guest molecule by shielding the excited state from non radioactive decay that normally occur in bulk aqueous solution. Similar observation of increase in fluorescence was observed in the case of 1-anilinonaphthalene-8-sulphonate on cyclodextrin complexation⁵. This was further possibly enhanced by the hydrogen bond formation between the carbonyl group of CIP with secondary hydroxyl function (fifth position) of BCD on complex formation and it was further confirmed by solubility and spectral studies reported earlier. Thus, the present study recommends the fluorimetric method for the analysis of CIP as CIP-BCD complex with higher sensitivity in trace quantity analysis of CIP either in formulations or in biological samples for bio-availability studies.

Experimental

Ciprofloxacin was obtained from Dr. Reddy's Research Foundation, Hyderabad, and Betacyclodextrin from Nippo Shokuhin, Tokyo, Japan and were used as such. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan, UV 240 spectrophotometer and Hitachi 650-1050, Japan, spectrofluorimeter were used.

Preparation of the physical mixtures and the complexes :

The physical mixtures were prepared in different ratios of CIP : BCD (w/w), 1 : 0.5, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 M and the neutralization complexes were prepared in the same ratio by separately dissolving the constituents in 0.01 M NaOH and mixing. HCl (0.01 M) was added slowly with constant stirring till complex separated out at pH 7.55. It was washed

and dried under vacuum.

UV spectroscopic analysis :

Solutions of Ciprofloxacin (5.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared in 0.1 M NaOH, water and 0.1M HCl and scanned in the UV range. Various preparations were also dissolved in 0.1 M NaOH to get a concentration 5.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and scanned for their λ_{max} in the UV range against a blank containing BCD. Standard plots for Ciprofloxacin and the formulations in the concentration range 0.0 to 10.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared at 272 nm. All the readings were taken in triplicate and the average was calculated. The molar extinction $a = A/ct$ (wherein A = absorbance, c = concentration in mol and t = path length in cm) and the percentage variation of a of the complexes with respect to the corresponding physical mixture (z) was also evaluated, using the formula,

$$z = \frac{(a_{\text{complex}} - a_{\text{physical mixture}})100}{a_{\text{physical mixture}}}$$

Fluorimetric analysis :

The fluorescence excitation and emission wavelengths for Ciprofloxacin (0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and its formulations in 0.01 M HCl, 0.01 M NaOH and water were evaluated using spectrofluorimeter. Standard plots were prepared in the concentration range 0.0 to 0.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ciprofloxacin and the formulations in triplicate in 0.01 M HCl at the excitation and emission wavelengths (278 and 448 nm respectively). An empirical fluorescence coefficient k was evaluated using the formula.

$$k = \text{Fluorescence intensity/concentration in mol.}$$

Note

The variation of k with respect to the physical mixture z was evaluated similar to that calculated for UV spectroscopic analysis.

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